

Enhancing Nursing Clinical Judgement

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Premise

- To understand what improves clinical judgment in nursing (students)
- Clinical Judgment:
 - Applied expression of nursing knowledge
- Situational Judgment:
 - Judgements within clinical settings
 - Integrative process

Premise

- Empirical review
 - Studies supporting the growth of CJ in the nursing domain
 - Not a systematic review
 - Thematic review
 - Primary focus on simulations

Contextual background

- Cognitive psychologist
 - Basic, theoretical, laboratory research
- National Council State Boards of Nursing (NCSBN)
 - Applied research (psychometrics)
 - Cannot control what knowledge/experience examinees bring to our assessment
 - Clinical judgment is situated within the content of our assessment.
 - Case studies
 - We must place strong structure on the assessment to promote high-level of reliability as well as validity.
 - Theoretical framework
 - Method of developing content—task models

Contextual background

Contextual background

- Task Models

- Reduces complexity and ambiguity by placing schemas on content
- Structured templates increase reliability of content
- Allows for generating many unique CJ items under different domains

Contextual background

- The review was written through a validity perspective and a psychometric perspective.
- Important because the tone might be misunderstood as overly critical rather than pragmatic.

Boundaries of Applied Research

- Control conditions
- Self-reported measures
 - Self-reported assessment of CJ
 - Metacognitive measures
- Comparability
 - Despite efforts for standardization, raters introduce challenges when comparing across studies
 - Meta-analysis techniques
- Timing

Boundaries of Applied Research

- Nurse educators identify as...
 - Educators first
 - Second clinicians (often required)
 - Third researchers, if they have additional capacity
 - Great opportunity for research collaboration
- Contrasts other fields where research comes first
 - Very few nursing research positions exist
 - Cost of entry into nursing research is high
- The majority of research reviewed is truly empirical research
 - Introduce a concept and see if it works

Measuring Clinical Judgment

- Lasater CJ Rubric
 - Noticing
 - Focused Observation
 - Recognizing Deviations from Expected Patterns
 - Information Seeking
 - Interpreting
 - Prioritizing Data
 - Making Sense of Data
 - Responding
 - Calm, Confident Manner
 - Clear Communication:
 - Well-Planned Intervention / Flexibility
 - Being Skillful
 - Reflecting
 - Evaluation / Self-Analysis
 - Commitment to Improvement

Simulations

- Manikins
 - Digital
- Standardized Patients
 - Trained *actors* reading tailored scripts

Quasi-experiments

- Methodology
 - Introduce participants to a simulation (multiple times) and measure CJ performance
 - Compare to Baseline or trends
- Show that participating in a (single) simulation improves CJ performance
- The question truly becomes why do participants improve?
 - Most studies include debriefing; could this be the driving factor for improvement?
 - Instructor engagement / mentorship?
 - Student engagement?
 - Experience? (Opportunities)
 - Simulations connect nursing theory with practice?